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A OVERVIEW ON AFFINITY CHROMATOGRAPHY: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Affinity chromatography is a separation technique that has become increasingly important in work with biological samples and pharmaceutical agents. Affinity chromatography is one of the most diverse and powerful chromatographic method for purification of a specific molecule or a group of molecules from a complex mixture by the specific interaction of solute with a ligand (which is immobilized). The affinity chromatography affords a means of characterizing interaction generated by an extremely broad range of binding affinities. In addition to its solute preparation and purification affinity chromatography thus also possess considerable potential for investigating the functional roles of the reactants there by purified. This review describes about the basic principle, procedure and its applications.

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INTRODUCTION

Combination of bio affinity and chromatography gave birth to affinity chromatography⁽¹⁾. Affinity chromatography is a type of liquid chromatography that makes use of biological-like interactions for the separation and specific analysis of sample components.^(2,3) The technique offers high selectivity, hence high resolution, and usually high capacity for the protein of interest. Purification can be in the order of several thousand-fold and recoveries of active material are generally very high.⁽⁴⁾

Affinity chromatography (also called affinity purification) makes use of specific binding interactions between molecules. A particular ligand is chemically immobilized or “coupled” to a solid support so that when a complex mixture is passed over the column, those molecules having specific binding affinity to the ligand become bound. After other sample components are washed away, the bound molecule is stripped from the support, resulting in its purification from the original sample. The basic idea has been widely exploited as a powerful tool for the separation and purification of a wide variety of biological macromolecules. Its effectiveness for purification rests on the selectivity of interaction, and thus of adsorption, of a biological macromolecule on an affinity adsorbent which is prepared by the covalent immobilization of a specific ligand on solid polymeric matrix.⁽⁵⁾

The selective isolation and purification of enzymes and other biologically important macromolecules by affinity chromatography exploits the unique biological property of the proteins to bind ligands specifically and reversibly⁽⁶⁾. Various methods are used to enrich or purify a protein of interest from other proteins and components in a crude cell lysate or other sample. The most powerful of these methods is affinity chromatography, also called affinity purification, whereby the protein of interest is purified by virtue of its specific binding properties to an immobilized ligand.⁽⁷⁾

Since the inception of affinity chromatography 50 years ago (Cuatrecasas et al, 1968), traditional purification techniques based on pH, ionic strength, or temperature have been replaced by this sophisticated approach. It has been stated that over 60% of all purification techniques involve affinity chromatography (Lowe, 1996). The wide applicability of this method is based on the fact that any given biomolecule that one wishes to purify usually has an inherent recognition site through which it can be bound by a natural or artificial molecule. Thus, we can say that affinity chromatography is principally based on the molecular recognition of a target molecule by a molecule bound to a column.

Affinity purification involves 3 main steps:

- a. Incubation of a crude sample with the affinity support to allow the target molecule in the sample to bind to the immobilized ligand.
- b. Washing away non-bound sample components from the support.
- c. Elution (dissociation and recovery) of the target molecule from the immobilized ligand by altering the buffer conditions so that the binding interaction no longer occurs.⁽⁸⁾

Affinity purification can provide significant time savings and several hundred-fold or higher purification, but success depends on the method used. Thus, it is important to optimize the purification protocol to achieve efficient capture and maximum recovery of the target.⁽⁹⁾

HISTORY OF AFFINITY CHROMATOGRAPHY:

In 1910, the German scientist, Emil Starckenstein published an article which described the concept of resolving macromolecule complexes via their interactions with an immobilized substrate. This manuscript discussed the influence of chloride on the enzymatic activity of liver α -amylase and opened the door for the early beginnings of this approach by several researchers (Arsenis & McCormick, 1966; Bautz & Hall, 1962; Campbell et al, 1951; Sander et al, 1966).

Affinity chromatography was first used in the isolation of enzymes in 1953 by Lerman.⁽¹⁹⁾ Later on, the term affinity chromatography introduced in 1968 by Pedro Cuatrecasas, Chris Anfinsen and Meir Wilchek in an article that briefly described the technique of enzyme purification via immobilized substrates and inhibitors (Cuatrecasas et al, 1968). Other early articles described the activation of a Sepharose matrix using a cyanogen bromide (CNBr) reaction (Axen et al, 1967) and the use of a spacer arm to alleviate steric hindrance (Cuatrecasas et al, 1968). Since 1968, affinity chromatography has become established as a standard laboratory technique for separation of enzymes.⁽¹⁰⁾ Affinity chromatography is still developing. It has played a central role in many “Omics” technologies, such as genomics, proteomics and metabolomics. The breakthrough development of affinity liquid chromatography has enabled researchers to explore fields such as protein–protein interactions, post translational modifications and protein degradation that were not possible to be examined previously. Finally, the coupling of reversed phase affinity chromatography with mass spectrometry has ultimately aided in discovery of protein biomarkers.⁽⁸⁾

METHODOLOGY:

Separation of a desired protein using affinity chromatography relies on the reversible interactions between the protein to be purified and the affinity ligand coupled to chromatographic matrix. As stated earlier, most of the proteins have an inherent recognition site that can be used to select the appropriate affinity ligand. The binding between the protein of interest and the chosen ligand must be both specific and reversible.

Fig. 1. Typical affinity chromatography purification.

A typical affinity purification is shown in Figure 1 and involves several steps. First, samples are applied under conditions that favor maximum binding with the affinity ligand. After sample application, a washing step is applied to remove unbound substances, leaving the desired (bound) molecule still attached to the affinity support. To release and elute the bound molecules, a desorption step is usually performed either 1) specifically using a competitive ligand or 2) non-specifically by changing the media atmosphere (e.g. changing the ionic strength, pH or polarity) (Zachariou, 2008). As the elution is performed, the purified protein can be collected in a concentrated form.

Bio molecules purified by affinity chromatography

Antibodies were first purified using affinity chromatography in 1951 when Campbell et al. used affinity chromatography to isolate rabbit anti-bovine serum albumin antibodies. For their purification, bovine serum albumin was used as the affinity ligand on a cellulose support. Two years later, this technique was expanded to purify mushroom tyrosinase using an immobilized inhibitor of the enzyme. Since then, affinity chromatography is commonly used to purify biomolecules such as enzymes, recombinant proteins, antibodies, and other biomolecules. Affinity chromatography is often chosen to purify biomolecules due to its excellent specificity, ease of operation, yield and throughput. In addition, affinity chromatography has the ability to remove pathogens, which is necessary if the purified biomolecules are to be used in clinical applications. The purity and recovery of target biomolecules is controlled by the specificity and binding constant of the affinity ligand. In general, the association constants of affinity ligands used for biomolecule purification range from $10^3 - 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1}$ (Janson, J-C, 1984). A common affinity ligand used in these purifications is an antibody, but other affinity ligands such as biomimetic dye-ligands, DNA, proteins and small peptides have been used as well. Figure 2 shows a wide variety of molecules that can be purified by affinity chromatography based on their polarity and volatility. The intrinsic biospecificity of macromolecule-ligand interactions has been a keystone in the development of affinity chromatography for the fractionation of proteins. It is now well documented that bio-specific interactions can be preserved in the immobilization of ligands, thus allowing the productive, differential binding of soluble proteins.⁽¹¹⁾

When affinity chromatography is used for the purification and separation of large biomolecules from complex mixtures, the support (matrix), spacer arms, and ligand must be considered.⁽⁸⁾

Affinity supports (Matrix):

For ligand attachment. Matrix should be chemically and physically inert.⁽¹²⁾ The selection and design of an affinity chromatographic method is the choice of support material. The supports used in affinity chromatography must meet the several requirements. Ideally, such a support should be inexpensive and allow solutes to have rapid, unhindered access to the immobilized affinity ligand. In addition, the support should play a completely passive role during the separation while also being able to couple the desired affinity ligand.⁽¹³⁾ Traditionally, affinity chromatography support materials have consisted of porous support materials such as agarose, polymethacrylate, polyacrylamide, cellulose, and silica. All of these support materials are commercially available and come in a range of particle and pore sizes. Some supports may be available with common affinity ligands already immobilized (e.g. protein A, Cibacron Blue, heparin). Other types of support materials are being developed including nonporous supports, membranes, flow-through beads (perfusion media), monolithic supports, and expanded-bed adsorbents.

Nonporous support materials consist of nonporous beads with diameters of 1- 3 μm . These supports allow for fast purifications, but suffer from low surface areas when compared to traditional porous supports.^(8,14)

Spacer arm:

Used to improve binding between ligand and target molecule by overcoming any effects of steric hindrance.⁽¹²⁾ Due to the fact that binding sites of the target molecule are sometimes deeply located and difficult to access due to steric hindrance, a spacer arm is often incorporated between the matrix and ligand to facilitate efficient binding and create a more effective and better binding environment. The length of these spacer arms is critical. Too short or too long arms may lead to failure of binding or even non-specific binding. In general, the spacer arms are used when coupling molecules less than 1000 Da.^(8,14)

Properties of ideal spacer arm:

1. It should be long enough (at least 3 atoms) to keep the substance at an appropriate distance.
2. It should be inactive not to cause a non-specific binding.
3. It should have bi functional group for the reaction with both support and the sample.⁽¹⁵⁾

To a foreign agent or antigen. Due to the variability of the amino acid sequence in the antibody binding si:

Figure 3.

Ligand:

Molecule that binds reversibly to a specific target molecule or group of target molecules.⁽¹¹⁾

Antibodies have several advantages including their high specificity and relatively large binding constants. Antibodies or immunoglobulins are a type of glycoprotein produced when a body's immune system responds to a foreign antigen (Fab regions shown in Figure 5), it has been estimated that antibodies can be produced for millions or even billions of different foreign agents. Antibodies which are produced by separate cell lines are referred to as polyclonal antibodies. Monoclonal antibodies are produced when a single antibody producing cell is combined with a carcinoma cell to create a hybridoma which can be grown in a cell culture. Monoclonal antibodies are often more desirable than polyclonal antibodies in affinity chromatography due to their lack of variability which allows for the creation of a more uniform affinity support.^(8,14)

Fig.4. Typical structure of an antibody. The amino acids in the Fc region generally have the same sequence, whereas the amino acids in the Fab region have variable amino acid sequences which allows for the specificity binding interaction against a wide range of antigens.

Another type of affinity ligand which can be used to purify biomolecules from complex mixtures is a dye-ligand. Dye ligand chromatography originated in 1968 when Haeckel et al. were purifying pyruvate kinase using gel filtration chromatography and found that Blue Dextran (a small dye molecule) co-eluted with the protein (Haeckel et al, 1968).^(8,14)

General Formats for Affinity Chromatography

The most common scheme for performing a separation in traditional affinity chromatography and HPAC is shown in Figure 5. First, a sample is injected onto the affinity column under conditions that allow strong binding by the target or analyte of interest with the immobilized ligand. These application conditions typically involve the use of an aqueous buffer that has a pH and ionic strength that mimic the native environment of the ligand and its target. Compounds in the sample that have little or no interaction with the ligand will elute from the column during this step, giving a non-retained peak. The next step utilizes an elution buffer to dissociate the target from the affinity ligand. This elution step often requires changing the mobile phase composition to promote target elution, as can be accomplished by altering the pH or by adding a competing agent to displace the target from the column. During this elution step, the released target can be collected for later analysis or use. If an HPLC support is used in the affinity column, it may also be possible during this step to monitor the eluting target directly by an on-line method. Both the on-line and off-line approaches can be combined with detection methods such as absorbance, fluorescence or mass spectrometry. After the target has been eluted, the column can then be regenerated prior to the next sample application by passing through the original application buffer.^(16,17)

Fig:5 The on/off elution format for affinity chromatography and a general chromatogram.

Immobilization of affinity ligands

The immobilized ligand is the key factor that determines the success of any affinity chromatographic method.⁽²⁾ When immobilizing an affinity ligand, care must be taken to ensure that the affinity ligand can actively bind the desired target after the immobilization procedure. Activity of the affinity ligand can be affected by multi-site attachment, orientation of the affinity ligand, and steric hindrance.

Multi-site attachment occurs when an affinity ligand is attached through more than one functional group on a single ligand molecule. If these multiple attachment sites cause the affinity ligand to become denatured or distorted, multisite attachment can lead to reduced binding affinity. However, in some instances, the additional attachment sites can result in more stable ligand attachment. In general, it is best to try for site-specific attachment of the ligands to limit the potential for multi-site attachment. For example, when immobilizing antibodies, covalent attachment is often directed toward the carbohydrate moieties within the Fc region of the antibody. Not only does this limit the number of attachment sites, but it can also help direct the binding and, thus, help orientate the antibody so the binding regions (Fab) are exposed. Another way to prevent multi-site attachment is to use a support that has a limited number of reactive sites. By limiting the reactive sites, the potential for multiple attachments from a single affinity ligand is greatly reduced. A general rule of thumb is the larger the affinity ligand to be immobilized, the fewer number of reactive sites on the support needed. Obviously, when performing affinity purifications, it is important to ensure the affinity ligands are immobilized so that the binding regions are exposed and free to interact and bind with the target molecule(s). Ideally, immobilization methods which specifically avoid attaching the affinity ligand via functional groups within the binding site(s) are used. One way to achieve this when immobilizing proteins is to use site-directed mutagenesis to introduce a single cysteine residue at a site known to be far away from the binding site(s).

Once the cysteine residue is introduced, the protein can be immobilized using a cysteine specific coupling reagent such as N-maleimidobutyl-oxysuccinimide ester.⁽²⁾

Fig. 6. Potential immobilization problems which can affect affinity ligand activity by a) multi-site attachment, (b) improper orientation, and (c) steric hindrance.⁽²⁾

Affinity Extraction

Another format that is often utilized for affinity chromatography in biomedical analysis is affinity extraction. In this approach, a specific analyte or group of analytes is removed or extracted from the sample by a column that contains an immobilized affinity ligand. The retained targets are then eluted and passed to a second method for analysis. Antibodies are often placed in columns for use in affinity extraction, giving a method known as an immunoextraction.

The technique of “affinity extraction” refers to the use of affinity chromatography for the isolation of a specific solute or group of solutes from a sample before their determination by a second analytical method.

Off-line affinity extraction

Off-line extraction is the easiest method for combining an affinity column with another analytical technique. This approach typically involves the use of an affinity ligand that is immobilized onto a low-performance support (e.g., activated agarose) that is packed into a small disposable syringe or solid-phase extraction cartridge. After the affinity column is conditioned with the necessary application buffer or conditioning solvents, the sample is applied and nonbound sample components are washed off of the packing, as shown in Fig. 1. An elution buffer is then applied, and the analyte is collected as it elutes from the column. In some cases, this eluted fraction is analyzed directly by a second technique, but in most situations the collected fraction is first dried and reconstituted in a solvent that is compatible with the method to be used for quantification. If needed, the collected solute fraction may also be derivatized before it is examined by other techniques to obtain improved detection or more appropriate physical properties (e.g., an increase in solute volatility before separation and analysis by GC).

The most common ligands in affinity extraction are antibodies, with the terms “immunoextraction” or “immunoaffinity extraction” often being used to refer to this particular extraction technique.

On-line affinity extraction

The direct coupling of affinity extraction with other analytical methods is yet another area that has been the subject of increasing research. The use of immunoextraction columns as part of HPLC systems has been of particular interest. The relative ease with which immunoaffinity columns can be incorporated into an HPLC system makes this appealing as a means for automating immunoextraction methods and for reducing the time required for sample pretreatment. In addition, the relatively high precision of HPLC pumps and injection systems provides on-line immunoextraction with better precision than off-line extraction methods, because the on-line approach has more tightly controlled sample application and elution conditions.⁽²⁾

Biokinetics of affinity chromatography

The reaction between the ligand (L) and target compound (T) in an affinity atmosphere (either adsorption or desorption) is represented in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Basic reaction between compound to be purified and ligand.(8)

Direct analyte detection by Affinity chromatography

For the detection sample of interest is first injected onto the affinity column under conditions in which the analyte will bind strongly to the immobilized ligand. This is usually done at a pH and ionic strength that mimic the natural environment of the ligand and analyte.

Boronate affinity chromatography

Boronate affinity chromatography is a separation method that uses a boronate as the affinity ligand.(6). Affinity methods that use boronic acid or boronates as ligands are one group of chromatographic techniques that have been used successfully with clinical samples. This group of methods, known collectively as “boronate affinity chromatography”.⁽²⁾

Lectin affinity chromatography

One particular technique that has seen growing interest over the last few years is lectin affinity chromatography. This is a type of affinity chromatography in which an immobilized lectin is used as the stationary phase. Lectins are non-immune system proteins that have the ability to recognize and bind certain types of carbohydrate residues. Lectins have often been used for sample pretreatment and target purification in applications where agarose is employed as the support.^(16,17)

One clinical application of lectin affinity chromatography has been in the separation and analysis of isoenzymes. A variety of other glycoproteins also have been studied and quantified by the use of lectin affinity columns.⁽²⁾

Immunoaffinity chromatography

Of all the types of affinity chromatography, those that use antibodies or antibody fragments as ligands make up the largest and most diverse group of affinity methods in clinical testing. The term “immunoaffinity chromatography” (IAC) is used for an affinity chromatographic method in which the stationary phase consists of an antibody or antibody-related reagent. When such a technique is performed as part of an HPLC system, the resulting method can be referred to as high-performance immunoaffinity chromatography (HPIAC).(8) There are several elution formats that can be utilized in immunoaffinity chromatography and HPIAC. The most common approach involves the step elution mode. Elution of the retained target in this case is often accomplished by using a change in the pH of the mobile phase, although the addition of a chaotropic agent or organic modifier can also be employed.

Protein a or protein g affinity chromatography

A third class of ligands that have been used in direct analyte detection by affinity chromatography are antibody-binding proteins such as protein A and protein G. These are bacterial cell wall proteins produced by *Staphylococcus aureus* and group G streptococci, respectively. These ligands have the ability to bind to the constant region of many types of immunoglobulins. Protein A and protein G bind most strongly to immunoglobulins at or near neutral pH, but readily dissociate from these solutes when placed in a buffer with a lower pH.⁽²⁾

Immobilized metal ion affinity chromatography

Immobilized metal ion affinity chromatography (IMAC) is another type of affinity chromatography that has seen growing use in biomedical analysis. IMAC makes use of the specific interactions that can occur between immobilized metal ions and targets such as amino acids, peptides, proteins, and nucleic acids. The metal ions are immobilized within a column through the use of chelating agents. IMAC was originally developed for the isolation and separation of metal- and histidine-containing proteins. During this type of analysis, the sample is passed through an IMAC column, and targets that can bind to the immobilized metal ions will be retained. These targets are later eluted through the addition of a competing agent (e.g., imidazole) and/or by changing the pH. IMAC has become a powerful tool for analyzing membrane proteins, histidine-tagged proteins, and phosphorylated proteins.

Analytical affinity chromatography

Besides its application for isolating and measuring specific targets, affinity chromatography can also be used to study interactions in biological systems. When affinity chromatography is utilized for this purpose, the method is referred to as analytical affinity chromatography, quantitative affinity chromatography or biointeraction affinity chromatography. One method that is often used to conduct these measurements is zonal elution. In this type of experiment, a small plug of a drug or analyte is injected onto an affinity column that contains the immobilized binding agent of interest. The retention factor or peak profile for the analyte is then analyzed under various conditions to obtain quantitative or qualitative information for a biological interaction.^(16,17)

Applications of Affinity chromatography:

Immunoglobulin purification (antibody immobilization)

Antibodies can be immobilized by both covalent and adsorption methods. Random covalent immobilization methods generally link antibodies to the solid support via their free amine groups using cyanogen bromide, N-hydroxysuccinimide, N,N'-carbonyldiimidazole, tressyl chloride, or tosyl chloride. Alternatively, free amine groups can react with aldehyde or free epoxy groups on an activated support. As these are random immobilization methods, the antibody binding sites may be blocked due to improper orientation, multi-site attachment or steric hindrance. Site-specific covalent immobilization of antibodies can be achieved by converting the carbohydrate residues located in the Fc region of the antibody to produce aldehyde residues which can react with amine or hydrazide supports.

Recombinant tagged proteins

Purification of proteins can be easier and simpler if the protein of interest is tagged with a known sequence commonly referred to as a tag. This tag can range from a short sequence of amino acids to entire domains or even whole proteins. Tags can act both as a marker for protein expression and to help facilitate protein purification.

GST tagged purification

Separation and purification of GST-tagged proteins is possible since the GST tag is capable of binding its substrate, glutathione (tripeptide, Glu-Cys-Gly).

When glutathione is reduced (GSH), it can be immobilized onto a solid support through its sulfhydryl group. This property can be used to crosslink glutathione with agarose beads and, thus, can be used to capture pure GST or GST-tagged proteins via the enzyme-substrate binding reaction (Beckett & Hayes, 1993; Douglas, 1987). Binding is most efficient near neutral physiological conditions (pH 7.5) using Tris saline buffer and mild conditions to preserve the structure and enzymatic function of GST. As a result of the potential for permanent denaturation, denaturing elution conditions are not compatible with GST purification. In addition, upon denaturation or reduction, the structure of the GST fusion tag often degrades.

His-tagged protein purification

Recombinant proteins which have histidine tags can be purified using immobilized metal ion chromatography (IMAC). The His-tag can be placed on either the N- or C-terminus. Optimal binding and, therefore, purification efficiency is achieved when the His-tag is freely accessible to metal ion support.

Protein A, G, and L purification

Proteins A, G, and L are native or recombinant proteins of microbial origin which bind specifically to immunoglobulins including immunoglobulin G (IgG). IgG represents 80% of serum immunoglobulins. The most popular matrixes or supports for affinity applications which utilize protein A, G, or L is beaded agarose.

Biotin and biotinylated molecules purification

If a biotin tag can be incorporated into a biomolecule, it can be used to purify the biomolecule using a streptavidin or avidin affinity support.

Affinity purification of albumin and macroglobulin contamination

Affinity purification is a helpful tool for cleaning up and removing excess albumin and α 2- macroglobulin contamination from samples since these components can mask or interfere with subsequent steps of analysis.^(8,14)

Enzyme isolation

There are a number of areas related to affinity chromatography that have also been of great interest in pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis. One such area is in the use of affinity columns for enzyme isolation. This approach may use affinity ligands that are substrates, inhibitors, cofactors, or proteins that are associated with the biochemical pathways of the target enzyme.^(6,9)

Protein and Peptide Separations

Affinity chromatography has a wide range of applications for protein purification, such as immunoaffinity, purification of immunoglobulins, purification of glycoproteins, DNA-binding proteins, receptor proteins, enzymes, cell isolation, and nucleotide isolation. Affinity chromatography is a specific purification technology based on biological function or individual chemical structure. The application of this technique is in separation of active biomolecules from denatured or functionally different forms in the isolation of pure proteins present at low concentration and also for removing specific contaminants.⁽¹⁸⁾

Investigating protein-protein interactions

Affinity chromatography provides one important method for identifying and characterizing the intermolecular interactions. When investigating protein-protein interactions, affinity chromatography typically involves linking one protein to an insoluble matrix and then incubating that matrix with a solution containing possible binding partners. This solution could be as simple as homogenous solution containing a single recombinant protein or complex. After incubating the immobilized substrate protein with its potential binding partner(s) and washing away material associated non specifically the binding partner are the eluted and detected by any variety of methods from chromatographic detection.⁽²⁰⁾

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